

A STUDY OF LEVEL OF MODERN THINKING IN FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS OF COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract:-

The concept of modernity is not only related with advance life style but also related with progressive thinking. Teachers and specially lady teachers can help girl students for development of modern thinking. So in present study survey is carried out to find out level of modern thinking in female student teachers. Standerdised tool is used to collect data. Measurement of central tendencies and distribution of percentage is calculated for statistical analysis. Sample is selected by random sampling method.

Title :- A Study of level of modern thinking in female student teachers of college of education.

Introduction:-

Female is the most depressed class in Indian society from ancient period. But after colonial period there were so many social reformers like mahatma phule, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, Dhondo keshav karve, Gopal Agarkar etc. these people were strongly spoke in fever of women and because of their efforts situation was started to change positively. In present there are large number of female teachers in society.

Objective of study:-

To find out level of modern thinking in female student teachers of college of education.

Importance of study:-

Concept of modern thinking is a broad concept. Modernity is related to thinking rather than life style. Many time we can see that person having advance life style in living but having orthodox mentality. Teacher plays important role in construction of mentality of students. Especially lady teachers can do more positive work for girls studying in school. So it is necessary find out level of modern thinking in female student teachers of college of education.

Research Methodology :-

Survey method is carried out for present study.

Sample and Sampling:-

A Sample of 120 female student teachers studying in college of education (A.Y. 2017-18) were selected by random sampling method from dhule and nandurbar city of Maharashtra state.

Tools of study:-

A tool for this study is modern thinking scale which is constructed by researcher. Standardization of

tool is also carried out by researcher. Reliability of modern thinking scale is 0.73 and face validity. There are 30 questions in this scale.

Statistical analysis:-

There was a score of tests filled by sample. By using this score mean, mode, median, standard deviation skewness and kurtosis value as well as distribution of percentage is calculated for checking of above mentioned objective.

Table no.- 1.To find out modern thinking attitude of female student teachers.

N	M	Mo	Mdn	S.D	Sk	Ku
120	115.43	113	115	13.74	0.09	0.33

- 1) In this test values of mean, mode and median are 115.43,113,115 respectively which are not same. So distribution is not normal
- 2) Value of kurtosis is 0.33 which is bigger than 0.263 so there is platykurtic type of curve.
- 3) Value of mean is bigger than median so it is positive skew curve.

Table no.-2.Distribution of female student teachers according to score in modern thinking test.

Sr. No.	Score	Interpretation	Student teachers
			Percentage
1	141 to 150	Very High Attitude	2%
2	121 to 140	High Attitude	36%
3	101 to 120	Moderate Attitude	49.70%
4	66 to 100	Low Attitude	12%
5	0 to 65	Very low Attitude	0.30%

Conclusion:-

As per responses noted by female student teachers to modern thinking scale, their level of attitude is found as mentioned below.

In very high attitude range 2%, in high attitude range 36%, in moderate attitude range 49.70% similarly 12% are in low attitude range and in very low attitude range 0.30 student teachers of female category are appeared.

Reference :-

- 1) Kadam C.P.(2007) – ShaikshanikSankhyashastra, Nityanutan Prakashan Pune.
- 2) Kayande Patil G.(2004) – SanshodhanPadhatti, Chaitanya publication, Nashik.